

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
AttMask	Attention-guided Masking
CPS	Counts per second
ICRP	International Commission on Radiological Protection
LLD	Low-Level Discriminator
MIM	Masked Image Modeling
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NORM	Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
(R)MSE	(Root) Mean Squared Error
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
SoA	State of the art
SUGI	Submarine Gamma Imager
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol / Internet Protocol
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
ViT	Vision Transformers

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Abstract

This deliverable delves into the intricate dynamics of radioactivity diffusion and transport in the marine environment providing firm grounds to develop physics-based simulation approaches. This cursory simulation model, together with a γ Sniffer sensor model, is then integrated in the overall RAMONES robotics simulator to obtain a functional simulation of the underwater glider and the γ Sniffer measurements when traversing a region of ocean with a certain concentration of radionuclides. The main aim of the simulation approach is to provide understanding of how radioactivity spreads in underwater ecosystems and support the development of advanced AI algorithms for the detection of a plume inside the underwater environment. Towards that end, these simulation results will form the initial data with which to train the AI-based software solutions that will output the subsequent regions of interest for the underwater gliders.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Natural radioactivity in the marine environment has been present since the Earth's formation, while artificial radionuclides were introduced in the ocean in 1944. More recent direct sources exist that feed the ocean, such as low-level liquid discharges from reprocessing plants, large scale due to disasters such as Fukushima and other smaller-scale radiological events. Moreover, the increasing utilization of nuclear energy nowadays has prompted an intensified focus on understanding and managing the potential environmental consequences of radioactivity. This part of the RAMONES work delves into the intricate dynamics of radioactivity diffusion and transport in the marine environment providing firm grounds to develop physics-based simulation approaches.

Interaction-free particle transport in the marine environment involves physical processes which can be based on Fick's law for diffusion, incorporating diffusion coefficients for salty water and velocity terms that consider the water currents in two or three dimensions. The main aim of the simulation approach developed in this work package (WP) is to provide understanding of how radioactivity spreads in underwater ecosystems and support the development of advanced AI algorithms for the detection of a plume inside the underwater environment.

In the present study, the crucial aspect of risk estimation is additionally considered by calculating the dose rates at each point within the simulated space. This quantitative measure enables the identification of critical areas and provides timely decision – making to prevent potential risks for human activity and health. The integration of *in situ* measurements ensures the reliability and applicability of the findings to real-world scenarios.

In the full scenario of diffusion and transport of radioactive substances in the marine environment, as for instance, in the case of a plume released from an underwater hydrothermal vent source, the physical characteristics of the radioactive substance (i.e. radioactive isotope) should be considered. Some of the well-established physical properties of anthropogenic or naturally occurring radioactive isotopes are directly connected to *their decay half-life*, which in turn is also directly connected to their perseverance in the marine environment.

Some of the basic laws governing the life cycle of a radioactive isotope, as well the environmental factors influencing the *natural half-life* in the marine world are briefly reviewed in the next paragraphs.

1.2. Radioactive decay law

Early in the history of the discovery of the phenomenon of radioactivity it was observed that the decay rate of a radioactive substance decreases exponentially. Suppose that N radioactive nuclei are present at time t without introducing any other nuclei into the sample. The number dN decaying in a time interval dt is proportional to N and so:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = -\lambda N \quad (1)$$

in which λ is a constant called the decay constant. If we divide by the number of nuclei N we get:

$$\lambda = -\frac{\frac{dN}{dt}}{N} \quad (2)$$

The right side of the above equation is the probability per unit time for the decay of one nucleus. Integrating Eq. 1 leads to the exponential law of radioactive decay, where $N_0=N(t=0)$.

$$N(t) = N_0 \exp(-\lambda t) \quad (3)$$

A useful quantity is the half time $t_{1/2}$ that provides the necessary time for the decay of the half number of nuclei. Putting $N=N_0/2$ in Eq. (3) we get:

$$\frac{N(0)}{2} = N_0 \exp \exp(-\lambda t_{1/2}) \Rightarrow t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln 2}{\lambda} \quad (3)$$

It is also useful to consider the mean lifetime τ , which is defined as the average time before the nucleus decays. The mean lifetime is given from the expression, $\tau=1/\lambda$. It should be mentioned that Eq. (3) refers to the number of undecayed nuclei remaining after time t . If we manage to observe a change ΔN in the number of the nuclei for time Δt then:

$$\Delta N = N(t) - N(t + \Delta t) = N_0 \exp \exp(-\lambda t)(1 - \exp(-\lambda \Delta t)) \quad (4)$$

If we suppose that $\Delta t \ll t_{1/2}$ we can ignore higher order terms in the expansion of the second exponential and so:

$$\Delta N = \lambda N_0 \Delta t \exp(-\lambda t) \quad (5)$$

We can also define the activity C to be the rate of the decays that occur in the sample.

$$C(t) = \lambda N(t) = \lambda N_0 \exp(-\lambda t) \quad (6)$$

Note that the activity can only provide the number of disintegrations per second and nothing about the kind of the emitted radiations or their energies. If we want to know about the effect of radiation in the biological system, activity is not a useful quantity since different radiations may give different effects.

The decay constant λ is a key parameter that determines the rate at which the radioactive substance transforms into a more stable state. After approximately $5t_{1/2}$, a noteworthy observation is the diminishing significance of the radioactive source's concentration resulting in a much-reduced impact of the source activity. It is crucial to note that the straightforward exponential model of radioactive decay is applicable only in specific situations where a particular initial amount of a substance undergoes decay to form a stable end product. In such cases, when a radioactive nucleus decays with a decay constant λ_1 to yield a stable nucleus 2, the count of remaining nuclei can be expressed as:

$$N_1(t) = N_0 \exp(-\lambda t), N_2 = N_0(1 - \exp(-\lambda t)) \quad (7)$$

There might be a case that nuclei of type 2 can also be radioactive and that is common in natural radioactive chains. So, if the given nucleus can decay in 2 steps until reaches a stable product, let's call these 2 decay modes a and b .

$$\lambda_a = \frac{\left(\frac{-dN}{dt}\right)_a}{N} \quad \lambda_b = \frac{\left(\frac{-dN}{dt}\right)_b}{N} \quad (8)$$

The total decay rate is then equal with:

$$-\left(\frac{dN}{dt}\right) = -\left(\frac{dN}{dt}\right)_a - \left(\frac{dN}{dt}\right)_b = N(\lambda_a + \lambda_b) \quad (9)$$

1.3. Natural radioactivity

Many of the known radioactive isotopes have half-lives that are compared with the age of the earth so we can still observe their radioactivity. The four natural chains of radioactivity, also known as radioactive decay chains or decay series, are intricate sequences of radioactive decay events that result in the transformation of one element into another. These chains are named after their initial, naturally occurring radioactive isotopes and are crucial components of the Earth's natural radioactivity.

- Uranium-238 (^{238}U) Decay Chain: Through a series of α , β decays reaches the stable isotope ^{206}Pb .

- Thorium-232 (^{232}Th) Decay Chain: undergoes alpha and beta decay steps, leading to the stable isotope ^{208}Pb . Radium and radon are among the intermediate elements.
- Uranium-235 (^{235}U) Decay Chain: undergoes alpha and beta decay processes, eventually reaching the stable ^{207}Pb . Intermediate elements include thorium and radium.
- Uranium-238 (^{238}U) Decay Chain: Similar to the first chain but starting with ^{237}Np and also ends in the stable nucleus ^{206}Pb .

1.4. Radionuclides in the marine environment

Covering slightly more than seventy percent of the Earth's surface, the ocean forms a vast interconnected expanse of water characterized by the presence of dissolved salts and suspended solids. This immense body of water is in constant motion, exhibiting a wide spectrum of movement, from the microscopic Brownian motions of molecules to turbulent eddies and extensive circulations associated with major ocean currents. The dispersion of substances, including radionuclides, within seawater is primarily influenced by two distinct processes: **advection** and **turbulent diffusion**.

Advection entails the physical displacement or movement of water, driven by the large-scale transport occurring in ocean currents. On the other hand, turbulent mixing arises from shear forces between different water bodies, leading to transport in a manner analogous to diffusion.

The most abundant radionuclide in sea water is by far ^{40}K with typical concentration to be approximately 12.2 Bq/L. Other natural radionuclides in sea water include ^{87}Rb , ^3H , ^7Be , ^{14}C , ^{22}Na and of course the decay chains mentioned in the previous paragraph. This work concerns not only natural sources of radioactivity, but also concentrations related with anthropogenic activities. The radionuclides of this category can be sorted into 2 groups: The first contains those which could have possible radiological impacts such as ^{90}Sr , ^{137}Cs , $^{238,239,240}\text{Pu}$ and are typically related to nuclear power plants waste or fallouts. The second group focuses on radionuclides that have been mainly used as radioactive tracers to study marine processes ^{99}Tc , ^{129}I (mostly related to medical procedures and fallouts).

1.5. Dosimetric quantities

The mean absorbed dose averaged over the volume of organs and tissues is the primary scientific quantity from which effective dose is calculated. Absorbed dose, D is defined as the quotient of mean energy dE imparted by ionizing radiation in a volume element and the mass dm of the matter in that volume:

$$D = \frac{dE}{dm} \quad (10)$$

The SI unit for absorbed dose is J/kg that is known as Gy. The equivalent dose to a tissue or organ is defined as:

$$H_T = \sum_R w_R D_{T,R} \quad (11)$$

Where w_R is the radiation weighting factor for radiation type R and $D_{T,R}$ is the mean absorbed dose from radiation type R in a tissue or organ T . Since w_R is dimensionless, the SI unit is the same with absorbed dose (J/kg) and its special name is Sievert (Sv).

The effective dose is the risk-related quantity in radiation protection and is defined as a weighted average of organ equivalent doses. It is computed as:

$$E = \sum w_T \left(\frac{H_T^M + H_T^F}{2} \right) \quad (12)$$

where H_T^M and H_T^F are the equivalent doses to the tissues of organs T and w_T is the weighting factor for target tissue T . It is measured in Sv as well as the equivalent dose and was originally introduced for the control of occupational exposures to external and internal sources of radiation.

1.6. Dose rate in the marine environment

Research and investigations into radiation dose rates in hydrothermal areas, particularly those associated with submarine hydrothermal vents, are conducted to understand the natural radioactivity present in these environments. These areas are characterized by the release of hot, mineral-rich fluids from the Earth's crust into the surrounding water, creating unique ecosystems.

Many studies have been conducted mostly in Japan to study the dose rates in sea water near Mariana and Okinawa trough. The dose rate in sea water was less than detection limit in the surface (less than 0.1 mGy/y), while it was around 2 mGy/y at the sea floor of hydrothermal area. The study was conducted with a dive of a submarine vehicle and there were locations at which the level of dose rate increased more than ten times exceeding the normal annual limit.

Other investigations have centered on gathering ocean sediments to assess concentrations of ^{226}Ra and ^{222}Rn , as well as other nuclides generated within the decay chains of uranium. The

concentrations typically fall within the range of approximately Bq/g, resulting in dose rates ranging from 1 to 20 mGy/y.

1.7. Dose limits

Establishing and adhering to dose limits for ionizing radiation is paramount for ensuring the safety and well-being of individuals who may be exposed to such radiation as part of their occupational activities. Ionizing radiation has the potential to cause harmful biological effects on living tissues, including damage to DNA and an increased risk of cancer. It seems crucial to maintain exposure levels as low as reasonably achievable, that is why protocols of radiation protection are so strict nowadays.

For the general public the annual dose rate limit is determined to be 1mSv/y and if we want to express it in terms of nSv/h is equal with 114 nSv/h. Both values are recommended from OSHA and ICRP. The limits for occupational dose limits are established to ensure the protection of radiation workers who may be exposed to ionizing radiation as part of their job. Both OSHA and ICRP recommend the annual dose limit for radiation workers to be set at 50 mSv/y. Converting in dose per hour means that is equal with 2280 nSv/h.

The inclusion of dose rate limits and guidelines in this section serves a critical purpose in our simulation, as it provides a foundation for understanding and applying the values associated with radiation exposure. As we embark on the calculation of dose rates and assess potential scenarios within the simulation, keeping these established limits in mind has a more general aspect than the present report.

2. Diffusion and Transport

Diffusion in liquids is a fundamental process governed by Fick's second law, which describes how solute particles move from regions of higher concentration to lower concentration within a liquid medium. This natural phenomenon is driven by the random thermal motion of molecules, leading to the spreading of substances and the establishment of concentration gradients. Fick's second law mathematically quantifies this process, expressing the rate of diffusion as proportional to the concentration gradient and the diffusion coefficient. In simpler terms, it states that the diffusion flux is directly proportional to the concentration gradient and inversely proportional to the molecular diffusion coefficient. This law is crucial in understanding various phenomena. In the simulations presented in the next sections we will use Fick's law to describe the diffusion of a radioactive concentration and the overall transport of substances in marine environments.

1.1. Fick's first and second laws

Fick's first law describes the rate of diffusion of a solute through a stationary medium and is given by the equation:

$$J = -D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \quad (13)$$

where J is the diffusion flux (amount of substance crossing unit area per unit time), D is the diffusion coefficient of the solute, C is the concentration of the solute, and $\frac{\partial C}{\partial x}$ is the concentration gradient.

Fick's second law builds upon the first law and the time factor. It describes how the concentration profile changes over time. We can extract Fick's second law using the continuity equation and Fick's first law:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial J}{\partial x} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \right) = 0 \quad \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \quad (14)$$

In the above:

- $\partial C / \partial t$ is the rate of change of concentration with respect to time.
- $\partial^2 C / \partial x^2$ is the second spatial derivative of concentration.
- D is the diffusion coefficient.

The last expression (Eq. 14) is Fick's second law and can be expanded in 3 dimensions:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \cdot \nabla^2 C \quad (15)$$

The transition from Fick's first law to the second law involves recognizing that the concentration gradient ($\partial C / \partial x$) is not constant, but changes with time. The second law (Eq. 15) introduces the concept that the rate of change of concentration with respect to time is proportional to the second spatial derivative of concentration. This accounts for the changing concentration profile over time as diffusion progresses.

1.2. Adding a transport term

In Fick's second law, a transport term can be incorporated to account for the convective transport of the diffusing species in addition to the diffusive process. The modified equation, often referred to as the transport-diffusion equation, is expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \cdot \nabla^2 C - \vec{u} \cdot \vec{\nabla} C \quad (16)$$

Here, the additional term $-\vec{u} \cdot \vec{\nabla} C$ represents the convective transport, where u is the fluid velocity. This convective term reflects the contribution of bulk fluid flow to the overall transport of the solute. When fluid motion is present, it influences the concentration distribution by advecting the solute along with the fluid. Incorporating the transport term into Fick's second law (Eq. 13) is essential for scenarios involving fluid flow. The transport-diffusion equation becomes a more comprehensive tool for describing the dynamic behavior of solute transport, considering both diffusive and convective phenomena.

The solution for the case of an instantaneous ($t=0$) and localized at ($x=0$) release in one dimension is:

$$C(x, t) = \frac{M}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} \exp \exp \left(-\frac{(x - ut)^2}{4Dt} \right) \quad (17)$$

Note that the direction of the advection may not be active at the same time as diffusion in the same direction. For example, in 2D, in the x direction there might be an underwater current. That means that there is advection only in x direction, but the diffusive spread also happens in the y direction as well, making these processes parallel.

1.3. Difference between advection and diffusion

Both advection and diffusion move the pollutant from one place to another, but each accomplishes this differently. The essential difference is that:

- Advection goes one way (downstream).
- Diffusion goes both ways (regardless of a stream direction).

This is seen in the respective mathematical expressions:

- Advection $u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}$ has a first order derivative, which means that if x is replaced by $-x$ the term changes signs (anti-symmetry).
- Diffusion $D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2}$ has a second-order derivative, which means that if X is replaced by $-x$ the term does not change sign (symmetry).

The main question is if both advection and diffusion can displace the pollutant, in which condition is one more effective than the other. That is, can we have cases of fast advection and relatively weak diffusion and other cases of fast diffusion and negligible advection? To answer that we must compare the sizes $u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}$ and $D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2}$ by introducing scales.

After these assumptions, advection term can be scaled as:

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \sim U \frac{C}{L} \tag{18}$$

Similarly, the diffusion term can be scaled as:

$$D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \sim D \frac{C}{L^2} \tag{19}$$

Table 1 - Scale to estimate and compare advection and diffusion

Variable	Scale	Choice of value
c	C	Average initial or boundary value of concentration
u	U	Max. value of velocity
x	L	Domain length

Equipped with these estimates, we can then compare the two processes by forming the ratio of their scales:

$$\frac{\text{advection}}{\text{diffusion}} = \frac{\frac{UC}{L}}{\frac{DC}{L^2}} = \frac{UL}{D} \quad (20)$$

This ratio is obviously dimensionless and is called the *Peclet* number:

$$PE = \frac{UL}{D} \quad (21)$$

If $PE \ll 1$ (in practice, if $PE < 0.1$), the advection term is significantly smaller than the diffusion term. Physically, diffusion dominates, and advection becomes negligible. The spread occurs almost symmetrically despite the directional bias of the (weak) flow. If we aim to simplify the problem, we can omit the $u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x}$ term, as if u were negligible. The relative error introduced in the solution by doing so is expected to be of the order of the Peclet number, and the smaller PE is, the smaller the error. Solutions established with diffusion only were based on such simplification and are valid as long as $PE \ll 1$.

If $PE \gg 1$ (in practice, if $PE > 10$), the advection term significantly outweighs the diffusion term. In this scenario, advection dominates, and diffusion becomes negligible, resulting in minimal spreading as the pollutant patch is merely transported along with the flow. To simplify the problem, we can omit the term $D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2}$, as if D were negligible. The relative error introduced in the solution by doing so is expected to be on the order of the inverse of the Peclet number ($1/PE$), and the larger PE is, the smaller the error. It's important to note that neglecting the term with the highest-order derivative reduces the need for one boundary condition. No boundary condition may be imposed at the downstream end of the domain, and whatever occurs there is determined by the flow.

If $PE \approx 1$ (in practice, if $0.1 < PE < 10$): the advection and diffusion terms are not significantly different, and neither process dominates over the other. No approximation to the equation can be justified, and the full equation must be utilized.

3. Simulation Technique

2.1. Diffusion

The solution of Fick's second law using finite differences involves discretizing the spatial and temporal domains and approximating the partial derivatives with respect to space and time. Fick's second law describes the diffusion of a substance in a medium, and its one-dimensional form is given by Eq. 14. To solve the equation numerically using finite differences we discretized the grid for both space and time. Considering a uniform grid with grid points x_i and time steps t_n , where i and n represent the indices of space and time respectively, the approximations of finite differences can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \approx \frac{C_i^{n+1} - C_i^n}{\Delta t} \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \approx \frac{C_{i+1}^n - 2C_i^n + C_{i-1}^n}{\Delta x^2} \quad (23)$$

Substituting these approximations into Fick's second law, we get:

$$\frac{C_i^{n+1} - C_i^n}{\Delta t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \approx D \frac{C_{i+1}^n - 2C_i^n + C_{i-1}^n}{\Delta x^2} \quad (24)$$

The above equation can be rearranged to solve for the concentration per volume at the next time step C_i^{n+1}

$$C_{i+1}^n = C_i^n + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} (C_{i+1}^n - 2C_i^n + C_{i-1}^n) \quad (25)$$

This numerical scheme (5.1) allows the calculation of the concentration at each spatial grid point and time step, providing a solution to the diffusion process described by Fick's second law. The accuracy of the solution depends on the chosen grid resolutions ($\Delta x, \Delta t$).

The finite difference method employed to solve Fick's second law is a numerical technique that, while versatile, is subject to certain limitations and errors. One primary source of error arises from the inherent approximation of continuous functions through discretization. A coarse grid might lead to significant truncation errors, especially in regions with rapid concentration changes, while an excessively fine grid can increase computational costs without proportionally enhancing accuracy.

Another potential source of error lies in the stability of the numerical scheme. The choice of time step (Δt) influences the stability of the method. If the time step is too large, it may violate stability conditions, resulting in numerical instability and inaccurate solutions. Conversely, an overly restrictive time step might unnecessarily slow down the simulation.

Moreover, the finite difference method assumes constant diffusion coefficients and uniform grid resolutions, which may not accurately represent real-world scenarios with varying material properties or irregular geometries. Despite these challenges, careful consideration of grid resolutions, stability criteria, and model assumptions can mitigate errors, allowing the finite difference method to provide valuable insights into diffusion processes while recognizing its inherent limitations.

Of course, if we want to expand in 2 or 3 dimensions, we must add the terms for y and z direction, respectively.

2D:

$$C_{i,j}^{n+1} = C_{i,j}^n + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} (C_{i+1,j}^n - 2C_{i,j}^n + C_{i-1,j}^n) + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y^2} (C_{i,j+1}^n - 2C_{i,j}^n + C_{i,j-1}^n) \quad (26)$$

3D:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{i,j,k}^{n+1} = & C_{i,j,k}^n + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} (C_{i+1,j,k}^n - 2C_{i,j,k}^n + C_{i-1,j,k}^n) \\ & + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y^2} (C_{i,j+1,k}^n - 2C_{i,j,k}^n + C_{i,j-1,k}^n) \\ & + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta z^2} (C_{i,j,k+1}^n - 2C_{i,j,k}^n + C_{i,j,k-1}^n) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

2.2. Adding the advection term

The one-dimensional Fick's law with an advection term is given by:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} - u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} \quad (28)$$

where u represents the advection velocity. If we extend the equation into 3 dimensions, it becomes:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 C - \vec{u} \cdot \vec{\nabla} C \quad (29)$$

By using central differences for the spatial derivatives of the advection term:

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} = u \frac{C_{i+1} - C_{i-1}}{2\Delta x} \quad (30)$$

We can now discretize the diffusion- advection equation accordingly and we should only consider the advection term either in one two or three dimensions:

$$C_i^{n+1} = C_i^n + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} (C_{i+1}^n - 2C_i^n + C_{i-1}^n) - \frac{u\Delta t}{2\Delta x} (C_{i+1}^n - C_{i-1}^n) \quad (31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{i,j}^{n+1} &= C_{i,j}^n \\ &+ D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} (C_{i+1,j}^n - 2C_{i,j}^n + C_{i-1,j}^n) - \frac{u_x \Delta t}{2\Delta x} (C_{i+1,j}^n - C_{i-1,j}^n) \\ &+ D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y^2} (C_{i,j+1}^n - 2C_{i,j}^n + C_{i,j-1}^n) - \frac{u_y \Delta t}{2\Delta y} (C_{i,j+1}^n - C_{i,j-1}^n) \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{i,j,k}^{n+1} &= C_{i,j,k}^n + D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} (C_{i+1,j,k}^n - 2C_{i,j,k}^n + C_{i-1,j,k}^n) - \frac{u_x \Delta t}{2\Delta x} (C_{i+1,j,k}^n - C_{i-1,j,k}^n) \\ &+ D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y^2} (C_{i,j+1,k}^n - 2C_{i,j,k}^n + C_{i,j-1,k}^n) - \frac{u_y \Delta t}{2\Delta y} (C_{i,j+1,k}^n - C_{i,j-1,k}^n) \\ &+ D \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta z^2} (C_{i,j,k+1}^n - 2C_{i,j,k}^n + C_{i,j,k-1}^n) - \frac{u_z \Delta t}{2\Delta z} (C_{i,j,k+1}^n - C_{i,j,k-1}^n) \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

The above Eq. (31)-(33) are the ones used in the simulation and provide a numerical solution for the concentration at each spatial grid point and time step.

2.3. Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy condition

In the realm of mathematics, the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy condition, often referred to as the CFL condition, is an essential requirement for achieving convergence in the numerical solution of specific partial differential equations, through finite difference methods. This condition becomes pertinent when employing explicit time-marching schemes for numerical solutions. Consequently, the time step must be constrained to be smaller than a specific threshold in numerous explicit time-marching computer simulations; otherwise, the simulation is prone to yielding inaccurate results.

To articulate the condition in a reasonably precise manner, it is essential to define specific quantities:

- **Spatial Coordinate:** This represents one of the coordinates in the physical space where the problem is formulated.

- Spatial Dimension of the Problem: denoted by 'n,' it signifies the number of spatial dimensions, corresponding to the spatial coordinates in the physical space.
- Time: This serves as a parameter describing the system's evolution, distinct from spatial coordinates.

Spatial coordinates and time are considered discrete-valued independent variables, with their minimal steps known as the interval length and time step, respectively. The CFL condition establishes a relationship between the time step and the interval lengths of each spatial variable.

In practical terms, the CFL condition is frequently applied to terms within the finite difference approximation of general partial differential equations that model the advection phenomenon

One dimensional case

In the context of one-dimensional scenarios, the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition takes the following expression:

$$C = u \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} \leq C_{max} \quad (34)$$

where C represents the dimensionless Courant number and:

- u is the velocity (with dimensions of Length/Time),
- Δt is the time step (with dimensions of Time),
- Δx is the length interval (with dimensions of Length)

The critical value C_{max} varies based on the method employed for solving the discretized equation. In explicit (time-marching) solvers, it is typically set to 1. Implicit (matrix) solvers are generally less susceptible to numerical instability, allowing for the acceptance of larger values of C_{max} .

The case for two or more dimensions

In the two-dimensional case the CFL condition becomes:

$$C = u_x \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x} + u_y \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y} \leq C_{max} \quad (35)$$

By analogy with the two-dimensional case, the general CFL condition for the n-dimensional case is the following one:

$$C = \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{u_{x_i}}{\Delta x_i} \leq C_{max} \tag{36}$$

Note that the interval length is not required to be the same for each spatial variable $\Delta x_i=1,2,\dots,n$. This degree of freedom can be used in order somewhat to optimize the value of the time step for a particular problem, by varying the values of the interval to avoid having it too small.

Other expression of the criterion

Without using the velocity terms, the CFL criterion can be described as:

$$C = \frac{D\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \leq C_{max} \tag{37}$$

Where D represents the diffusion coefficient, Δt is the time step and Δx is the spatial step. The quantity $\frac{D\Delta t}{\Delta x^2}$ is dimensionless. If it exceeds C_{max} the numerical solution may become unstable. The common value for C_{max} is $1/2$ for stability in explicit numerical methods, including finite difference schemes for solving partial differential equations. This condition, often referred to as the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) stability criterion, is a guideline to prevent numerical instability.

In summary, $C \leq 1/2$ is a standard stability criterion, and it ensures that the time step is small enough to capture the relevant dynamics in the system without causing instability in explicit numerical schemes.

Figure 1 - Schematic diagram explaining the CFL criteria for a three-point scheme. (Left) An unstable three point scheme. The shaded region shows the numerical domain of dependence which does not contain the true domain of dependence (Right) A stable three-point

2.4. Parameter tuning

The diffusion coefficient for radionuclides in seawater can vary depending on the specific radionuclide and environmental conditions. Generally, the diffusion coefficients for radionuclides in water are relatively low compared to diffusion in air. For example, the diffusion coefficients for radionuclides like ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr in seawater are estimated in the range of 10^{-9} – 10^{-12} m^2/s . However, these values are approximate, and the actual diffusion coefficient can depend on factors such as temperature, salinity, and the chemical form of the radionuclide. We present a table with typical values for the diffusion coefficient of some nuclei.

Table 2 - Diffusion coefficient values for radioactive nuclei for various temperature values

isotope	D (10^{-10} m^2/s)		
	0°C	18°C	25°C
^3H	56.1	81.7	93.1
^{40}K	9.86	16.7	19.6
^{137}Cs	10.6	17.7	20.7
^{90}Sr	3.72	6.70	7.94
^{131}I	10.3	17.2	20.0
^{226}Ra	1.02	7.45	8.89
^{232}Th	--	1.53	--

As can be seen in Table 2, the diffusion coefficient increases with an increase in temperature, and this phenomenon is described by the Arrhenius equation. The Arrhenius equation relates the rate constant (or diffusion coefficient in the case of diffusion) to temperature and is expressed as follows:

$$D = D_0 \exp \left(-\frac{E_a}{RT} \right) \quad (38)$$

Eq. 38 indicates an exponential dependence of the diffusion coefficient on the inverse of temperature ($1/T$). As the temperature increases, the term $1/T$ decreases, leading to an increase in the diffusion coefficient. The underlying explanation lies in the increased kinetic energy of particles at higher temperatures. With higher thermal energy, particles have greater mobility and are more likely to overcome energy barriers, facilitating the diffusion process. This relationship is commonly observed in various diffusion phenomena, including the diffusion of gases, liquids, and solutes in solids.

Since our simulation takes into account the diffusion coefficient, we made a linear regression for every isotope targeted, based on the literature values as to obtain the diffusion coefficient value for every temperature needed. An example is being presented for ^{137}Cs in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 - Diffusion coefficient vs temperature diagram for ^{137}Cs

Although we only have three experimental values the linear correlation shown in that plot, it seems to describe accurately the monotonous change in the diffusion coefficient:

$$D = 0.40T + 10.57$$

The low values of the diffusion coefficient make diffusion in seawater a very slow process, opposite to what is valid for diffusion in the atmospheric air. The diffusion coefficient D is a fundamental parameter describing the rate at which a substance disperses through a medium. This discrepancy is primarily attributed to the stark differences in viscosity between the two mediums. Air, being a less dense and more mobile medium, allows for faster molecular movement, resulting in higher diffusion coefficients.

On the other hand, seawater, characterized by its higher viscosity due to the presence of salts and other dissolved substances, impedes molecular diffusion, leading to significantly lower diffusion coefficients. Temperature, in particular, tends to have a notable impact, with higher temperatures generally correlating with increased diffusion coefficients. Understanding these

differences is crucial when assessing the transport and dispersion of substances, such as radionuclides, in different environmental settings.

In the marine environment, water currents, tides, and other dynamic processes play a significant role in transporting substances. These advective processes can lead to the rapid movement of particles or dissolved materials over relatively long distances. While diffusion still occurs in seawater, its impact is smaller than advection.

Typical values of water currents in marine environments can vary widely depending on factors such as location, depth, and proximity to coastlines. In open ocean, average current speeds may range from a few centimeters per second to several kilometers per hour. Coastal areas have strong complexity and may experience stronger sea currents. For instance, tidal currents in coastal zones can reach velocities exceeding one meter per second, emphasizing the dynamic nature of water flow in these regions.

As discussed earlier, the values for spatial grid spacing Δx and time step Δt selected accordingly to the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition for ensuring numerical stability in explicit time-marching schemes. By carefully selecting those values the numerical stability needed to conduct the simulation is guaranteed. The results are shown in the next section.

2.5. Dose conversion factors

Dose Conversion Factors (DCF) play a crucial role in assessing the potential health risks associated with exposure to radionuclides. These factors provide a conversion between the concentration of a radionuclide in a specific environmental medium and the resulting dose to individuals or populations. The DCF is expressed in units of sieverts per unit concentration Sv/Bq, representing the radiation dose received per unit of radioactive material.

The DCF accounts for factors such as the radionuclide's decay properties, energy emitted per decay, and biological effectiveness in different tissues. It allows estimation of the effective dose to humans from environmental contamination.

It is important to note that DCF values can vary among different radionuclides and depend on factors such as the route of exposure, age, and gender of the exposed population. These factors contribute to the complexity of accurately assessing radiation risk from environmental sources. In our analysis we will use the mean values that were found in literature and not consider the different tissue that is exposed. In Table 3 we present values for the effective dose rate coefficients for each radionuclide.

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Table 3 - Effective dose rate coefficients for water immersion

isotope	Effective dose rate coefficients (10^{-17} Sv m ³ /Bq h)
³ H	1190
¹⁴ C	1.02
⁴⁰ K	59400
⁹⁰ Sr	38.5
¹³⁷ Cs	37.1
²²² Rn	12.6
²²⁶ Ra	211
²³² Th	5.25
²³⁴ U	4.18
²³⁸ U	2.27
²³⁸ Pu	2.41
²⁴⁰ Pu	2.35

4. Results of the simulated diffusion and advection

In the present analysis, we begin by presenting plots depicting background spectra in the marine environment. These spectra are generated by sampling Monte Carlo (MC) values from a Gaussian distribution, providing a comprehensive understanding of the natural radiation levels. Additionally, to account rare events, we introduce exotic events into the simulations by incorporating their probabilities. This inclusion enhances the realism of the model, allowing us to explore scenarios beyond typical background conditions. The goal of this section was to create time series of counts per second or dose rate through time for other goals of the project.

In the next stage we will focus on the diffusion of an initial concentration through time and space. Simulations using Fick's law were engaged to capture the evolution of the radioactivity spread in the marine environment. We will present snapshots from animated simulations and tables presenting values of concentration in specific places of the simulated space.

Building upon our exploration of Fick's law, our analysis progresses to incorporate realistic transport terms influenced by actual water currents within the marine ecosystem. This augmentation introduces a dynamic layer to our simulations, reflecting the interplay between diffusion and the physical transport of radioactivity.

By incorporating genuine velocity currents into our numerical models, we aim to provide a more accurate representation of the complex mechanisms governing the dispersion of radionuclides. In a manner parallel to our earlier simulations, we will present snapshots extracted from animated simulations. These snapshots will enable a direct and insightful comparison between the processes of diffusion alone and the combined effects of diffusion and transport.

Finally, in the last section based on the previous analysis, our investigation takes a focused turn towards specific grid points within our simulated marine environment. In this section, we will present comprehensive tables detailing the temporal evolution of radionuclide concentrations at these selected points. We will further calculate the corresponding dose rates, offering a quantitative measure of radiation exposure risk at these strategic locations. Results are shown in the next section.

3.1. Background and exotic events spectra

In this study, time series plots have been generated to depict the fluctuation of dose rates and concentration per liter in a marine environment adjacent to a geothermic spring. These plots serve as visual representations illustrating how atypical events could manifest within the

spectral time series data. To simulate these events, a Monte Carlo (MC) method has been employed, introducing a parameter indicative of the likelihood of such occurrences. By adjusting this parameter, the probability of anomalous events can be systematically varied, enabling the examination of their potential effects on both dose rates and concentration levels over time. This approach offers a nuanced understanding of the dynamics and the associated risks stemming from sporadic deviations in radiation levels near geothermal springs.

Figure 3 - Monte-Carlo time series of dose rate in the marine environment

Figure 4 - Monte-Carlo time series of concentration in the marine environment

Figure 5 - Monte-Carlo time series of dose rate in the marine environment

Figure 6 - Monte-Carlo time series of concentration in the marine environment

Having demonstrated the generation of events through a probabilistic process in the previous section, our study will now proceed to create simulated events in one, two, or three dimensions in the subsequent section. By leveraging this approach, we aim to investigate the advection-diffusion dynamics of the phenomenon, drawing upon Fick's second law of diffusion and advection principles. Through this analytical framework, we will explore how the simulated events propagate and disperse over time and space, providing valuable insights into the transport mechanisms governing the phenomenon.

3.2. 1D simulation

In this paragraph we present an example of a simulation to investigate the diffusion behavior of ^{137}Cs in the marine environment. The simulation was performed taking into consideration the diffusion coefficient for ^{137}Cs at a temperature of 17°C , a critical factor influencing the transport dynamics in sea water. Following the simulation, we present a heatmap illustrating the diffusion pattern of ^{137}Cs after one and two days, providing valuable insights into its dispersion and movement over time. In addition to that we will present a plot illustrating the concentration profile of ^{137}Cs across spatial dimension following the two days of diffusion.

In subsequent analyses, we will extend our investigation beyond diffusion alone by considering the influence of water currents on the transport of ^{137}Cs in the marine environment. Specifically, we will incorporate a water current with an intensity of 2 cm/s into our simulation model. By integrating this additional factor, we aim to capture the combined effects of diffusion and advection on the dispersion of ^{137}Cs . To visualize the spread of concentration resulting from this coupled transport process, we will present a heatmap illustrating the distribution of ^{137}Cs after one minute of simulation time. Additionally, we will generate a plot depicting the concentration profile of ^{137}Cs across spatial dimensions following the same one-minute interval.

Figure 7 - 1D Diffusion of ^{137}Cs at $T=17^\circ\text{C}$ after 2 days

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Figure 8 - 1D Spread of concentration due to diffusion after 2 days for ¹³⁷Cs at T=17°C after 2 days

Figure 9 - 1D Diffusion and Transport of ¹³⁷Cs at T=17°C with u=2 cm/s after 5 s.

Figure 10 - 1D Diffusion and Transport of ¹³⁷Cs at T=17°C with u=2 cm/s after 1 min

Figure 11 - 1D Spread of concentration due to transport after 1 minute for ¹³⁷Cs at 17°C and u=2 m/s

3.3. 2D simulation

In this paragraph we explore the diffusion dynamics of ^{40}K in the marine environment through a two-dimensional (2D) simulation. We initialize the simulation with an initial concentration of ^{40}K and a radius of 1 cm. Throughout the simulation, we track the diffusion of ^{40}K over time, capturing snapshots of the phenomenon at daily intervals for a duration of five days. Each snapshot offers a visual representation of the spatial distribution of ^{40}K concentration as it diffuses within the marine medium. Subsequently, we analyze the concentration profile at the final time-step, spanning from the center of the grid to the edge with a step size of 2 cm. This examination allows us to assess the evolution of ^{40}K concentration across spatial dimensions, shedding light on the extent of diffusion and the spatial variability of concentration within the marine environment. Parameters such as the diffusion coefficient at 16°C are carefully considered in our simulation setup to ensure the accuracy and relevance of our findings.

In addition, we will proceed by initializing a concentration of ^{40}K at the spatial location ($x=10$ cm, $y=10$ cm) inside the water. Incorporating water currents with velocities $u_x = u_y = 1$ cm/s we aim to investigate the influence of advection on the dispersion of ^{40}K after one minute of simulation time. Additionally, we will present concentration profiles at the specified location $x=10$ cm and $y=10$ cm at the final time-step. Furthermore, we will generate concentration profiles at adjacent spatial locations by incrementing the space step by 20 cm, providing insights into the spatial variability of ^{40}K concentration within the marine environment.

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Figure 12 - Diffusion of ⁴⁰K, initial concentration

Figure 13 - Diffusion of ⁴⁰K, after 1 d

Figure 14 - Diffusion of ⁴⁰K, after 2 d

Figure 15 - Diffusion of ⁴⁰K, after 3 d

Figure 16 - Diffusion of ⁴⁰K, after 4 d

Figure 17 - Diffusion of ⁴⁰K, after 5 d

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Figure 18 - Time series of concentration in positions $x=10$ cm and $y=10$ cm

Figure 19 - Time series of concentration in positions $x=10$ cm and $y=12$ cm

Figure 20 - Time series of concentration in positions $x=10$ cm and $y=14$ cm

Figure 21 - Time series of concentration in positions $x=10$ cm and $y=16$ cm

Figure 22 - Time series of concentration in positions $x=10$ cm and $y=18$ cm

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Figure 23 - Advection of ^{40}K at $t=0$

Figure 24 - Advection of ^{40}K at $t=15\text{ s}$

Figure 25 - Advection of ^{40}K at $t=30\text{ s}$

Figure 26 - Advection of ^{40}K at $t=45\text{ s}$

Figure 27 - Advection of ^{40}K at $t=60\text{ s}$

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Figure 28 - Time series of concentration in positions $x=10$ cm and $y=10$ cm

Figure 29 - Time series of concentration at $x=30$ cm and $y=30$ cm

Figure 30 - Time series of concentration at $x=50$ cm and $y=50$ cm

Figure 31 - Time series of concentration at $x=70$ cm and $y=70$ cm

3.4. 3D simulation - the case of Kolumbo submarine volcano

In this simulation, we will replicate the dynamics of the Kolumbo volcano near Santorini, focusing on the dispersion of ^{222}Rn isotopes commonly associated with underwater volcanic activity. We will generate an initial concentration equal with 50 kBq/L distribution at the seabed and observe the advection phenomenon over a 5-minute period, considering a vertical water current of 0.5 m/s. Throughout the simulation, we will provide snapshots of concentration and dose rate profiles for every minute along the z-axis. By incorporating advection, diffusion, and decay processes specific to ^{222}Rn , we aim to model the dispersion of this radioactive isotope within the water column. The concentration profiles obtained from the simulation will provide insights into the spatial distribution of ^{222}Rn , highlighting how underwater volcanic emissions propagate and disperse in marine environments. Additionally, we will analyze the corresponding dose rate profiles at various steps along the z-axis to

examine the spatial distribution of ^{222}Rn and its corresponding radiological impact at different depths within the water column.

By analyzing concentration and dose rate profiles at multiple depths, we aim to understand the vertical variability in ^{222}Rn dispersion and its potential consequences for marine organisms and human activities. This comprehensive approach allows us to assess the depth influence on the transport dynamics and radiological implications of underwater volcanic emissions, providing valuable insights into the environmental and health risks associated with ^{222}Rn exposure in marine ecosystems. Through this detailed examination, we seek to elucidate the complex interplay between depth-dependent processes and the distribution of ^{222}Rn isotopes, advancing our understanding of the factors driving the behavior of underwater volcanic emissions and their impact on marine environments.

In presenting the concentration and dose rate profiles obtained from the simulation, it's important to note that these profiles have been processed to isolate the signal originating from the simulated event while rejecting any background noise or interference. By carefully filtering out extraneous signals and background radiation, we ensure that the concentration and dose rate profiles accurately represent the influence of the simulated ^{222}Rn dispersion within the water column. This rigorous approach enables us to focus exclusively on the impact of the volcanic emission event, providing a clear and precise depiction of the spatial and temporal distribution of ^{222}Rn and its associated radiological effects.

The provided 3D snapshots vividly depict the temporal evolution of the radiological phenomenon within the water column over the simulated 5-minute period. Initially, at the commencement of the simulation, localized regions of elevated dose rates emerge near the seabed, reflecting the release of ^{222}Rn isotopes from the volcanic source. As time progresses, these regions expand and disperse, indicative of the advection and diffusion processes at play. Notably, the snapshots capture the dynamic nature of the dispersion phenomenon, with dose rate distributions evolving in both spatial and temporal dimensions.

Moreover, the 3D snapshots allow for the observation of gaps and variations in dose rate distributions, highlighting the heterogeneous nature of the radiological phenomenon. These gaps, resulting from the transport of higher concentrations at faster rates. As the simulation progresses, the gaps become more pronounced, reflecting the differential transport rates of ^{222}Rn within the water column.

Also, the dose rate profiles, extracted from the concentration profiles multiplied with the dose coefficient for ^{222}Rn , offer a comprehensive assessment of the radiological impact associated with the simulated ^{222}Rn dispersion. By analysing dose rates at various depths within the water

column over time, we gain a nuanced understanding of the spatial distribution of radiological hazards posed by underwater volcanic emissions. The dose rate profiles exhibit distinct temporal trends, reflecting the temporal evolution of ^{222}Rn concentrations and their corresponding radioactive decay. Initially, higher dose rates are observed near the seabed, reflecting the elevated concentrations of ^{222}Rn emanating from the volcanic source.

However, as time progresses, the dose rates exhibit a more homogeneous distribution across different depths, indicative of the diffusion and dispersion of ^{222}Rn throughout the water column. These profiles reveal distinct patterns, with dose rates peaking close to the volcanic source and gradually decreasing with increasing distance. Notably, dose rate signals reach remarkably high levels, exceeding 60 nSv/h in proximity to the source, before attenuating as distance from the source increases. This spatial variation in dose rate distributions underscores the localized radiological impact of underwater volcanic emissions, with dose rates diminishing with distance from the volcanic origin. We will end our analysis by adding the background because of the ^{40}K concentration. The plotted data showcases dose rates in a marine environment resulting from the release of ^{222}Rn concentration, while also considering background radiation stemming from ^{40}K . This makes the outcome closer to real world scenario by also adding white noise in the data points of our signals. The final plots are shown below.

Figure 32 - Initial plume distribution at the bottom of the Kolumbo volcanic cone

Figure 33 - Plume evolution after 1 min

Figure 34 - Plume evolution after 2 min

Figure 35 - Plume evolution after 3 min

Figure 36 - Plume evolution after 4 min

Figure 37 - Plume evolution after 5 min

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Figure 38 - Dose rate profile at z=20 m

Figure 39 - Dose rate profile at z=40 m

Figure 40 - Dose rate profile at z=80 m

Figure 41 - Dose rate profile at z=120 m

3.5. Short summary

The results of the plume simulations in terms of the advection-diffusion dynamics can be summarized briefly in the following paragraphs.

Firstly, our simulations reveal that advection is a significantly stronger phenomenon than diffusion within the marine environment. This observation underscores the influential role of seawater viscosity in shaping transport processes, with advection exerting a dominant influence over diffusion. The calculation of the Peclet number, a dimensionless parameter quantifying the ratio of advection to diffusion, further supports this assertion, with values significantly exceeding 1. This emphasizes the prominence of advection-driven transport mechanisms in marine environments, highlighting the importance of considering fluid dynamics in environmental studies, esp. when radioactive material spreading is involved.

Our findings highlight a crucial distinction between the behaviors observed in water and air environments. In contrast to the marine setting where advection significantly outweighs diffusion, resulting in a Peclet number substantially greater than 1, the dynamics in air environments exhibit a more balanced relationship between diffusion and advection. Here, the Peclet number approaches unity, indicating that diffusion and advection processes are relatively equal in magnitude.

Secondly, our analysis includes the calculation of time series data for dose rates derived from simulated events. These time-series provide valuable insights into the potential consequences of radioactive events occurring in the marine environment. By examining the temporal evolution of dose rates resulting from simulated events, we gain a deeper understanding of the potential impacts and risks associated with such occurrences. These insights are instrumental in informing risk assessment and management strategies, facilitating proactive measures to mitigate the potential effects of radioactive events on marine ecosystems and human populations.

Overall, our findings underscore the importance of integrating multidimensional modeling approaches with empirical data to comprehensively assess and address environmental risks associated with geothermic activity and radioactive events in marine environments.

One notable strength of the developed model lies in its capability to generate comprehensive time series data, depicting both dose rates and concentration per liter across every point in space based in the parameters of initial concentration of the simulated event, the temperature that affects the diffusion coefficient and the water currents affecting the motion of the occurring concentration. This feature offers an unprecedented level of spatial resolution, enabling detailed insights into the distribution and evolution of radiation levels and substance concentrations over time.

In future research endeavors, the validation of our model's predictions will be paramount in enhancing our understanding and management of potential risks associated with radioactive events in marine environments near hydrothermal vents.

5. Simulation Results for Manoeuvring Scenarios

In this section we present simulation results for the RAMONES γ Sniffer sensor radiological activity, expressed in “counts per second” (CPS), in glider manoeuvres traversing a hydrothermal vent plume. These combine glider trajectories, and we present both an actual trajectory and a simulated one, with the space-time radioactive nuclei concentration diffusion for a hydrothermal vent obtained in Section 4.4 – 3D simulation - the case of Kolumbo submarine volcano.

A ROS node acting as a proxy for the γ Sniffers sensor has been developed which outputs the CPS (counts per second) measurement based on the defined acquisition interval (10 seconds for the γ Sniffers in RAMONES missions) and the AUG progression during that time period. The 4D matrix computed in the previous section is used to map from x-y-z position and time to ^{222}Rn concentrations. The sensor then integrates the expected instantaneous CPS based on the ^{222}Rn concentrations and activity and outputs the average CPS during the integration time.

4.1. Actual glider manoeuvre and simulated CPS measurements

For the AUG manoeuvre we used one of the manoeuvres performed during the engineering trials detailed in *D2.3 – Final report on Positioning, Cooperative Control and Navigation*. It corresponds to a section of a lawnmower manoeuvre, comprising line segments and half a circumference, as depicted in **Figure 42**. The plume was positioned in a way the AUG transverses it during the manoeuvre, at an approximately constant height. Points inside the plume are plotted in a color gradient corresponding to the ^{222}Rn concentration, which is correlated with CPS.

Figure 43 shows the simulated sensor measurements for a γ Sniffer like the ones installed in the actual AUGs for RAMONES. The conversion from ^{222}Rn concentration to CPS for the specific γ Sniffer used in RAMONES is the one established in Section 2. For the simulated scenario, the separation between *inside* and *outside* the plume is clear, with typical CPS inside the plume being about 5x larger than typical CPS due to natural background radiation. Moreover, the radioactivity sensed inside the plume is so large that it is always larger than the background radiation by a wide margin. This situation makes it easy to detect when the AUG is inside a plume and define its surrounding volume as a new zone of interest for future mapping and source detection manoeuvres.

Figure 42 - 3D plot of a constant height AUG maneuver and its transversion of a hydrothermal vent plume

Figure 43 - Simulation of measured CPS by the RAMONES gamma spectrometer sensor during the AUG's lawn mower maneuver

The second scenario contemplates a glider descending in a helicoidal path within a water volume containing the plume resulting from water diffusion of particles released by a hydrothermal vent. The AUG path and plume shape are depicted in **Figure 44**. The resulting measured CPS by the simulated RAMONES γ Sniffer are plotted in **Figure 45**. A cursory look at **Figure 45** reveals five time intervals where the measured radiation is clearly above the background level, with the CPS plot presenting a *hill shape*, although not symmetric or regular in height. These outliers from background radiation correspond to a mix of two phenomena. First, as seen in **Figure 44**, the glider is not always within the plume at a constant distance from its center but transverses it repeatedly, going from outside the plume to sections close to the plume center and returning outside, repeatedly. Second, the plume radioactive elements concentration is time varying, as concentrated pulses of elements diffuse on their way to the surface. It is the combination of these phenomena that is the source of the irregularities of the measured CPS.

4.2. Conclusions

The results of the plume simulations using the advection-diffusion dynamics from the previous section allowed to perform realistic simulations for the conditions to be encountered inside the Kolumbo volcano regarding the γ Sniffer measurements based on the dispersion of ^{222}Rn isotopes commonly associated with underwater volcanic activity.

Both actual and simulated maneuvers were used as basis for transversing the advection-diffusion plume containing radioactive ^{222}Rn . Simulation results show that there is a clear distinction between “inside the plume” and “outside the plume”, with CPS for gamma radiation measurements being almost an order of magnitude above background radiation.

The clear signal difference perceived by the simulated γ Sniffer sensor when traversing the hydrothermal vent plume gives credence that the RAMONES goal of detecting underwater natural occurring radioactivity can be achieved. Furthermore, it sustains the feasibility using the γ Sniffer CPS measurements to guide the RAMONES system to output a new zone of interest for the underwater glider to map, in an effort to pinpoint the radioactivity source.

Figure 44 - 3D plot of a helicoidal AUG path descending through the hydrothermal vent plume

Figure 45- Simulation of measured CPS by the RAMONES gamma spectrometer sensor during the AUG's helicoidal maneuver through the hydrothermal plume.

6. Updates to the AI-based solutions for time series and imaging data analysis

5.1. MLP-based Sparse Measurements Interpolation

An updated architecture of the MLP that offers improved performance has been used for the mapping of the radioactivity distribution. The reference architecture has been updated to an MLP with four hidden layers, of which the first two consist of 512 neurons, while the third and fourth consist of 256 and 128 neurons respectively. The ReLU activation function was considered for the hidden layers. The MLP is optimized considering the L1-smooth loss function with respect to the measured values in the corresponding spatial locations. A small portion of the available data (<5%) is considered as validation data and an early stopping strategy is implemented, with patience equal to 10 epochs. The early stopping helps to prevent the model from overfitting, thus allowing better approximation of values far from the measured locations. As before, the three-dimensional input coordinates are transformed based on Fourier Features to capture higher spatial frequencies of the radioactivity distribution.

To assess radioactivity mapping algorithms, the simulation environment presented in D4.3 was used, considering different types of underwater glider trajectories and different radioactivity distributions. A grid of query coordinates was considered consisting of $31 \times 31 \times 8 = 7688$ regularly spaced points. The aim was to keep a reasonable trade-off between horizontal (XY plane) and vertical (Z axis) resolution due to memory restrictions. Based on the considered volume size and use cases it was much more costly to improve the horizontal resolution than the vertical. Therefore, the spatial resolution in XY was ≈ 100 m and in Z it was as dense as possible based on computational constraints. The updated architecture improved the radioactivity mapping accuracy by 13% on average with respect to the method reported in D4.3 on the reference signals considered there, without any significant impact on the temporal and memory efficiency. The source code of the developed radioactivity mapping method is provided in the ramones_eu GitHub repository "*Efficient Neural Gamma Radioactivity Mapping*" (ENeGMa) <https://github.com/ramones-eu/ENeGMa> (private access).

5.2. Scan Region Definition via Radioactivity Mapping and Detection

Two strategies were considered for defining search regions for the RAMONES gliders based on the γ Sniffer measurements and the MLP-based mapping products. Both strategies were tested during the Kolumbo expedition on the 27th and 28th of October 2024.

The first strategy involved performing an Adaptive Exponential Moving Average (AEMA) on the stream of on-line γ Sniffer measurements collected by the glider as it moves in the water, in order to detect and localize significant changes, possibly corresponding to radioactivity hotspots. The proposed method is implemented as a ROS node designed for real-time anomaly detection in gamma radiation. It processes incoming radiation data (counts), calculates a dynamic EMA to monitor trends, and identifies anomalies by comparing deviations against thresholds derived from a gamma distribution. The thresholds are periodically recalibrated using recent data to ensure accuracy. When an anomaly is detected, the script logs the event and publishes it. This tool is ideal for applications requiring continuous monitoring of radiation levels. The AEMA approach has been selected over other possible choices, including z-score, Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average, and Long-Short Term Memory recurrent neural networks, as AEMA offered an optimal balance between accuracy and efficiency (both time-wise and memory-wise), given that the method needs to run on the limited-resources onboard processing unit of the glider (Raspberry Pi 4 single-board computer) to enable near-realtime decision-making regarding anomaly detection. The initial thresholds were tuned based on data collected during the Milos expedition. Specifically, off-line estimation of break points has been performed on the previously collected data, using dynamic programming and employing an L2 norm. A hyper-parameter search of the EMA model has been then performed, aiming to match the reference detected break points of the signal. The source code of the corresponding ROS node has been integrated in the γ Sniffer repository at: <https://github.com/ramones-eu/gsniffer> (private access).

The second approach involved is based on the radioactivity mapping, as computed by the data collected by the RAMONES gliders. The approach introduces three-dimensional volumes (generalized voxels) to confine the trajectories of the vehicles, where increased radioactivity levels are being observed, in relation to the radioactivity map constructed using the ENeGMA reconstruction method. By processing the γ Sniffer data collected during previous missions with the MLP-based approach, a dense three-dimensional radiation point cloud was produced (**Figure 46**). By covering the scanned volume with generalized voxels, whose dimensions were determined based on the mission needs and the preliminary analysis using the developed high-level simulation environment, metrics were computed for each voxel regarding the radiation data points within them. The considered metrics included average and total counts per time frame. A visualization of the most prominent generalized voxels was then conducted, enabling to define search regions for the upcoming glider missions to obtain more detailed maps of the radioactivity distribution, where necessary.

Figure 46 - 3D radiation data points accompanied by the most active three-dimensional generalized voxels

5.3. Radioactivity monitoring in the hydrothermal field of Kolumbo

This section reports radioactivity mapping and monitoring results based on the data captured during the 3rd mission performed in the underwater of Kolumbo on Oct. 27th. The mission involved a crucial dive to a depth of 465 meters (spanning from 465-100-465 meters), using the γ Sniffer instrument. The collected data is illustrated in the figures below, detailing depth variations and radiation levels.

In particular, the scatter plot (Figure 47) presents CPS distribution across different depths. It can be observed that, while lower and moderate values are spread relatively evenly, distinct

peaks are evident in some water layers. The first notable peak appears around 150 meters, while the most pronounced peaks occur below 400 meters, close to the hydrothermal field of Kolumbo which lies at 500 meters depth. This indicates an increased presence of gamma radiation in these regions.

Figure 48 and **49** display reconstructed radioactivity distribution maps based on the data collected, using the ENeGMa method described above. These plots depict CPS activity along the dive path and its surrounding area, reinforcing the earlier observations of heightened radiation near the crater's base, particularly in the hydrothermal field, as well as between 100 and 200 meters.

Finally, **Figure 50** presents the generalized voxels fitted in the reconstructed radioactivity map, indicating regions of interest and suggesting candidate locations for possible subsequent scans from the glider vehicles. Candidate regions corresponding to lower radioactivity levels are represented with darker colours, while candidate regions shown with lighter colours correspond to higher radioactivity levels.

Figure 47 - γ Sniffer CPS distribution from spiral dive at (465-100-465 m) target depth on October 27th

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Figure 48 - 3D plot of radioactivity distribution on the glider trajectory from the helicoidal dive during the 3rd (465-100-465 meters) mission on October 27th. Darker colors indicate low activity and lighter high activity.

Figure 49 - 3D plot of radioactivity distribution in the immediate vicinity around the glider trajectory from the helicoidal dive during the 3rd (465-100-465 meters) mission on October 27th. Darker colors indicate low activity and lighter high activity.

Figure 50 - Color-coded generalized voxels fitted on the radioactivity mapping of the 3rd (465-100-465 m) mission on October 27th. Darker voxels indicate low activity and lighter high activity.

7. References

- TJ Mertzimekis, Paraskevi Nomikou, E Petra, Pedro Batista, David Cabecinhas, A Pascoal, L Sebastião, J Escartín, Konstantin Kebkal, Konstantinos Karantzalos, et al. Radioactivity monitoring in ocean ecosystems (ramones). In *Proceedings of the Conference on Information Technology for Social Good*, pages 216–220, 2021.
- D Calmet. *Radionuclides released into coastal waters*. International Atomic Energy Agency, 1985.
- Yogesh Girdhar, Anqi Xu, Bir Bikram Dey, Malika Meghjani, Florian Shkurti, Ioannis Rekleitis, and Gregory Dudek. Mare: Marine autonomous robotic explorer. In *2011 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, pages 5048–5053. IEEE, 2011.
- Radiation Effects Branch. Monitoring of nuclear contamination in arctic seas. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Monitoring of Nuclear Contamination in Arctic Seas*, volume 18, page 19, 1995
- I Puillat, S Sparnocchia, P Farcy, R Bozzano, M Borghini, L Coppola, S Cusi, N Medeot, R Nair, M Ntomas, et al. Jerico: A joint European research infrastructure network for coastal observatories supporting marine research in the mediterranean sea.
- Kenneth S Krane. *Introductory nuclear physics*. John Wiley & Sons, 1991
- Carlos A Bertulani. *Nuclear physics in a nutshell*. Princeton University Press, 2007
- W Noel Cottingham and Derek A Greenwood. *An introduction to nuclear physics*. Cambridge University Press, 2001
- K Kovler, H Friedmann, B Michalik, W Schroeyers, A Tsapalov, S Antropov, T Bituh, and D Nicolaides. Basic aspects of natural radioactivity. In *Naturally occurring radioactive materials in construction*, pages 13–36. Elsevier, 2017
- Devadattiah Devaputra, Thomas G Thompson, and Clinton L Utterback. The radioactivity of sea water. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 7(3):358–366, 1932
- Hirok Chaudhuri, Nisith K Das, Rakesh K Bhandari, Prasanta Sen, and Bikash Sinha. Radon activity measurements around Bakreswar thermal springs. *Radiation Measurements*, 45(1):143–146, 2010
- Hugh D Livingston and Pavel P Povinec. Anthropogenic marine radioactivity. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 43(8-9):689–712, 2000
- Peter Atkins and Julio De Paula. *Elements of physical chemistry*. Oxford University Press, USA, 2013
- International Commission on Radiological Protection. Dose coefficients for external exposures to environmental sources. *Ann ICRP*, 49(2):1–147, 2020

- Shin Toyoda, Debabrata Banerjee, Hidenori Kumagai, Junichi Miyazaki, Junichiro Ishibashi, Nobutatsu Mochizuki, and Shigeaki Kojima. Gamma ray doses in water around sea floor hydrothermal area in the southern Mariana trough. *Subseafloor Biosphere Linked to Hydrothermal Systems: TAIGA Concept*, pages 603–606, 2015.
- Ai Uchida, Shin Toyoda, Jun-ichiro Ishibashi, and Shun'ichi Nakai. ²²⁶Ra-²¹⁰Pb and ²²⁸Ra-²²⁸Th dating of barite in submarine hydrothermal sulfide deposits collected at the Okinawa trough and the southern Mariana trough. *Subseafloor Biosphere Linked to Hydrothermal Systems: TAIGA Concept*, pages 607–615, 2015.
- Linda Schenk, Sven Ove Hansson, Christina Rudén, and Michael Gilek. Occupational exposure limits: A comparative study. *Regulatory toxicology and pharmacology*, 50(2):261–270, 2008.
- Anthony D Wrixon. New ICRP recommendations. *Journal of Radiological Protection*, 28(2):161, 2008.
- Richard Courant. Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy condition. 2018
- Tony F Chan. Stability analysis of finite difference schemes for the advection-diffusion equation. *SIAM journal on numerical analysis*, 21(2):272–284, 1984
- Li Yuan-Hui and Sandra Gregory. Diffusion of ions in sea water and in deep-sea sediments. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 38(5):703–714, 1974
- A Poisson and A Papaud. Diffusion coefficients of major ions in seawater. *Marine Chemistry*, 13(4):265–280, 1983
- Gerhard Neumann. *Ocean currents*. Elsevier, 2014
- Victor Klemas. Remote sensing of coastal and ocean currents: An overview. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 28(3):576–586, 2012
- Kimiaki Saito, Nobuhito Ishigure, Nina Petoussi-Hens, and Helmut Schlattl. Effective dose conversion coefficients for radionuclides exponentially distributed in the ground. *Radiation and environmental biophysics*, 51:411–423, 2012
- Keith F Eckerman, Anthony B Wolbarst, and A CB Richardson. Limiting values of radionuclide intake and air concentration and dose conversion factors for inhalation, submersion, and ingestion: Federal guidance report no. 11. Technical report, Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, DC (USA), 1988.
- MB Bellamy, SA Dewji, RW Leggett, M Hiller, K Veinot, RP Manger, KF Eckerman, JC Ryman, CE Easterly, NE Hertel, et al. External exposure to radionuclides in air, water, and soil. *Federal Guidance Report 15*, 402, 2019.